

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
TPS	Training Platform Specification
OE	Ontology Engineering
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
DSS	Decision Support System
ORSD	Ontology Requirements Specification Document
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations
XSL-FO	Extensible Stylesheet Language Formatting Objects
XDM	XML Documentation Markup
KB	Knowledge Base
DBMS	Database Management System

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the first version of the SatisFactory knowledge model for human resource optimization. There will be a final version of the knowledge model at M18.

The first part of this document is devoted to the Purpose, Context and Scope of this Deliverable. Later, we present information about the background and State Of the Art in Ontology Engineering and Semantic Modelling. We investigate the objectives and benefits as well as the definition and main components of Semantic Modelling. We present methodologies for building ontologies and the major ontology languages as well as the leading ontology tools. We use W3C standards for the Semantic Web in order to link data, create vocabularies, query and Inference. Next, we present Ontology Design through NeOn methodology. For the creation of the SatisFactory Ontology Network, we use three scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Ontologies built from scratch
This section includes ontologies for the Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants for chemical processes, the recognition of accidents and path optimization for workers' movement and the development of "on Job" training/educational environment.
- Scenario 2: Ontologies built from non-ontological resources
This section includes ontologies for the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) which includes R3D and B2MML XML Schemas.
- Scenario 3 : Reusing Ontology networks
This section includes the ontology networks for Human Resource Management and the Context Management Ontology Network.

Finally, the last part of this deliverable focuses on Ontology Exploitation through Knowledge Visualization, Data Integration, Rules inferences, Context-Driven Information Acquisition and the alignment with existing ontological resources.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

In the framework of this project, the shop-floor knowledge management represents the core process of the SatisFactory platform, where different data (structured and unstructured) have to be exchanged from and towards many different sources.

The main goal of this task is to capture implicit and explicit knowledge at the shop-floor level. Thus, knowledge modelling methods, like ontology engineering (OE), are used in order to perform this task. All actors involved at this stage, as well as processes and assets, are defined. Concepts and relations between them are the basis of the knowledge modelling approach. Sets of rules coming from prior “hands-on” knowledge and previous experience enrich the knowledge model in order to achieve human resource optimization. Primarily, the model has to be both human and machine understandable. This is achieved with the use of semantic technologies in T2.2 and T3.1.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The background of the work described in this deliverable is mainly related to the following tasks and deliverables:

- D1.2 Use Case analysis and application scenarios description
- T1.4 Common Information Data Exchange Model
- T2.5 Development of "on job" training/educational environment
- T3.5 Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System

Hence the following deliverable aims to present different designing and modelling aspects of the Semantic Context Manager, such as:

- Modelling languages and standards
- Ontology development methodologies and tools
- SCM internal architecture
- Low level ontology concepts definition
 - Classes
 - Object Properties
 - Data Properties
- Ontology exploitation examples

Figure 1 Input and Output Block Diagram of D2.2

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 ONTOLOGY ENGINEERING

In the past 20 years, ontologies and their development have been the centre of attention. Ontology development has indeed become an engineering discipline. Ontology Engineering, refers to “The set of activities that concern the ontology development process and the ontology lifecycle, the methods and methodologies for building ontologies, and the tool suites and languages that support them” [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2011].

2.2 SEMANTIC MODELLING

2.2.1 Objectives and benefits

The logical data structure of a so-called database management system (DBMS), whether hierarchical, network, or relational, cannot totally satisfy the requirements for a conceptual definition of data, because it is limited in scope and biased toward the implementation strategy employed by the DBMS. Therefore, the need to define data from a conceptual view has led to the development of semantic data modeling techniques. That is, techniques to define the meaning of data within the context of its interrelationships with other data. The real world, in terms of resources, ideas, events, etc., is symbolically defined within physical data stores. A semantic data model is an abstraction, which defines how the stored symbols relate to the real world. Thus, the model must be a true representation of the real world. The overall goal of semantic data models is to capture more meaning of the data. Benefits of exploiting them for business applications are mainly:

- Avoiding misunderstanding, by providing a clear, accessible, agreed set of terms, relations as a trusted source and discussions so that misunderstandings can easily be resolved.
- Conduct reasoning, being machine understandable, and through the usage of logic statements (rules), ontology enable automatic reasoning and inference which leads to automatic generation of new and implicit knowledge.
- Leverage resources, by extending and relating an application ontology to external ontological resources, via manual or automatic mapping and merging processes, the need for repetition of entire design process for every application domain is eliminated.
- Improve interoperability, semantic models can serve as a basis for schema matching to support systems interoperability in close environments where systems, tools and data sources have no common recognition of data type and relationships.

Ontologies play an important role for many knowledge-intensive applications, since they provide formal models of domain knowledge that can be exploited in different ways. Ontology development has become an engineering discipline, Ontology Engineering, which refers to "The set of activities that concern the ontology development process and the ontology life cycle, the methods and

methodologies for building ontology, and the tool suites and languages that support them [D. Kiritsis, 2011].

2.2.2 Definition and main components

The term “ontology” was taken from Philosophy, where it means a systematic explanation of being. There are many definitions about what an ontology is and such definitions have changed and evolved over the years. However, Studer and colleagues [Studer et al., 1998] provide one of the most well-known definitions: “An ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization”. *Conceptualization* refers to an abstract model of some phenomenon in the world by having identified the relevant concepts of that phenomenon. *Explicit* means that the type of concepts used, and the constraints on their use are explicitly defined. *Formal* refers to the fact that the ontology should be machine-readable. *Shared* reflects the notion that an ontology captures consensual knowledge, i.e. it is not private for some individual, but accepted by a group”.

Ontologies can be modeled with different knowledge modeling techniques and they can be implemented in various kinds of languages based on different knowledge representation formalisms. It is important to mention here that there are connections and implications between the knowledge modeling components (concepts, roles, etc.) used to build an ontology, the knowledge representation paradigms (frames, description logics, logic) used to formally represent such components, and the languages used to implement the ontologies under a given knowledge representation paradigm. However, they share the following minimal set of components:

- **Classes** represent concepts, which are taken in a broad sense. For instance, in the domain of Energy Efficiency at Buildings, concepts are Building, Door, Window, Device, Sensor, etc. Classes in the ontology are usually organized in taxonomies through which inheritance mechanisms can be applied. We can represent a taxonomy of sensors (Scanning Sensor, Optical Sensor, Touch Trigger Sensor, etc.) or different types of doors in buildings (Inner Door, Outer Door, Sliding Door, Rotating Door, or Strong room Door).
- **Relations** represent a type of association between concepts of the domain. They are formally defined as any subset of a product of n sets, that is: $R \subset C_1 \times C_2 \times \dots \times C_n$. Ontologies usually contain binary relations. The first argument is known as the domain of the relation, and the second argument is the range. For instance, the binary relation *locatedIn* has the concept Building as its domain and the concept Location as its range; in addition, this relation can have the concept Device as domain. Binary relations are sometimes used to express concept attributes (aka slots). These attributes (*name*, *version*, *weight*, etc.) are usually distinguished from relations (*isComposeOf*, *hasConstraint*, *hasParameters*, etc.) because their range is a datatype, such as string, number, etc., while the range of relations is a concept.
- **Formal axioms**, according to [Gruber et al., 1993], serve to model sentences that are always true. They are normally used to represent knowledge that cannot be formally defined by the other components. In addition, formal axioms are used to verify the consistency of the ontology itself or the consistency of the knowledge stored in a knowledgebase. Formal axioms are very useful to infer new knowledge. An axiom in the Energy Efficiency at Buildings domain could be that it is not possible to build a public building without a fire door (based on legal issues).
- **Instances** are used to represent elements or individuals in an ontology.

2.2.3 *Foremost methodologies for building ontologies*

METHONTOLOGY², On-To-Knowledge³, and DILIGENT⁴ were up to 2009 the most referred methodologies for building ontologies. These methodologies mainly include guidelines for single ontology construction ranging from ontology specification to ontology implementation and they are mainly targeted to ontology researchers. In contrast to the aforementioned approaches, a new methodology, called the NeOn⁵ Methodology, suggests pathways and activities for a variety of scenarios, instead of prescribing a rigid workflow.

The **NeOn Methodology** [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa , 2010] for building ontology networks is a scenario-based methodology that supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments. A network of ontologies is a collection of ontologies related together via a variety of relationships such as alignment, modularization, version and dependency. The key assets of the NeOn Methodology are:

- A set of nine scenarios for building ontologies and ontology networks, emphasizing the reuse of ontological and non-ontological resources, the reengineering and merging, and taking into account collaboration and dynamism.
- The NeOn Glossary of Processes and Activities, which identifies and defines the processes and activities carried out when ontology networks are collaboratively built by teams.
- Methodological guidelines for different processes and activities of the ontology network development process, such as the reuse and reengineering of ontological and non-ontological resources, the ontology requirements specification, the ontology localization, the scheduling, etc. All processes and activities are described with (a) a filling card, (b) a workflow, and (c) examples.

METHONTOLOGY [A. Gomez-Perez, 2004] enables the construction of ontologies at the knowledge level. It includes (a) the identification of the Ontology Development Process – ODP – which tasks should be performed when building ontologies; (b) a life cycle based on evolving prototypes; and (c) some techniques to carry out management, development-oriented, and support activities. In addition, METHONTOLOGY includes a list of activities to be carried out during ontology reuse and re-engineering processes, but it does not provide detailed guidelines for such activities, nor does it consider different levels of granularity during the reuse of ontological resources (e.g., modules or statements). Moreover, METHONTOLOGY neither considers the reuse and re-engineering of non-ontological resources nor the reuse of ODP.

The **On-To-Knowledge** methodology [S. Staab et al.,2001] proposes to build ontologies taking into account how these are going to be used in knowledge management applications. The processes proposed by this methodology are the following: feasibility study, kickoff, where ontology requirements are identified, refinement, where a mature and application-oriented ontology is produced, evaluation, and maintenance. With respect to the reuse of knowledge resources, in the

² <http://semanticweb.org/wiki/METHONTOLOGY>

³ <http://www.ontotext.com/research/otk>

⁴ <http://semanticweb.org/wiki/DILIGENT>

⁵ <http://www.neon-project.org/>

kickoff process it is mentioned that developers should look for potentially reusable ontologies. However, this methodology does not provide detailed guidelines for identifying such ontologies nor for reusing them. Besides, the methodology neither explicitly mentions guidelines for the reuse and re-engineering of non-ontological resources, nor for the reuse of ontology design patterns.

The **DILIGENT** methodology [H. S. Pinto et al., 2001] is intended to support domain experts in a distributed setting in order to engineer and evolve ontologies. This methodology is focused on collaborative and distributed ontology engineering. Its ontology development process includes the following five activities: building, local adaptation, analysis, revision, and local update. With regard to the reuse of knowledge resources, the methodology does not include guidelines for the reuse and re-engineering of existing knowledge resources.

2.2.4 *Major ontology languages*

Different ontology languages have different expressiveness and inference mechanisms, since the knowledge representation paradigms underlying all these languages are diverse. Therefore, one of the key decisions to take in the ontology development process is to select the language (or set of languages) in which the ontology will be implemented.

Next, an overview of the current specifications for ontology languages developed in the scope of the W3C Semantic Web Activity (<http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/>) is presented.

RDF.

RDF [G. Klyne et al, 2004] stands for Resource Description Framework. It was developed by the W3C to create metadata for describing web resources and its data model is equivalent to the semantic networks formalism, consisting of three object types: resources, properties and statements.

RDF Schema.

The RDF data model does not have mechanisms for defining the relationships between properties and resources. This is the role of the RDF Vocabulary Description language [R. Guha, 2004] also known as RDF Schema. RDF(S) is the term commonly used to refer to the combination of RDF and RDFS. Thus, RDF(S) combines semantic networks with frames but it does not provide all the primitives that are usually found in frame-based knowledge representation systems.

OWL.

OWL [M. Dean et al., 2004] is the result of the work of the W3C Web Ontology Working Group. This language derived from DAML+OIL [F. van Harmelen et al, 2001] and, as the previous languages, is intended for publishing and sharing ontologies in the Web. OWL is built upon RDF(S), has a layered structure and is divided into three sublanguages: OWL Lite, OWL DL and OWL Full. OWL is grounded on Description Logics [F. Baader, 2003] and its semantics are described in two different ways: as an extension of the RDF(S) model theory and as a direct model-theoretic semantics of OWL. Both of them have the same semantic consequences on OWL ontologies.

OWL 2.

OWL 2 [B. Motik et al., 2009] is an extension and revision of OWL that adds new functionality with respect to OWL; some of the new features are syntactic sugar (e.g., disjoint union of classes) while others offer new expressivity. OWL 2 includes three different profiles (i.e., sublanguages) that offer important advantages in particular application scenarios, each trading off different aspects of OWL's

expressive power in return for different computational and/or implementation benefits. These profiles are:

OWL 2 EL

It is particularly suitable for applications where very large ontologies are needed, and where expressive power can be traded for performance guarantees.

OWL 2 QL

It is particularly suitable for applications where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to access the data directly via relational queries (e.g., SQL).

OWL 2 RL

It is particularly suitable for applications where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to operate directly on data in the form of RDF triples.

OWL 2 provides two alternative ways of assigning meaning to OWL 2 ontologies: the Direct Semantics that assigns meaning directly to ontology structures and the RDF-Based Semantics that assigns meaning directly to RDF graphs.

SPARQL

Even if it is not an ontology language, we mention SPARQL [E. Prud'hommeaux et al, 2008] here because it supports querying the previous languages. SPARQL allows performing queries over RDF data and, since both RDF-S and OWL are based in RDF, also over RDF-S and OWL ontologies. SPARQL can be used to express queries across diverse data sources and its syntax is similar to SQL to facilitate its adoption.

2.2.5 *Leading ontology tools*

Focus is given on the new generation of ontology engineering environments, particularly, on Protégé, described hereafter. They have extensible, component-based architectures, where new modules can easily be added to provide more functionality to the environment.

Protégé⁶ is an open platform for ontology modeling and knowledge acquisition. It is an open source, standalone application with an extensible architecture. The core of this environment is the ontology editor, and it holds a library of modules that can be plugged, called plug-ins, to add more functions to

Figure 2 Protégé Logo

the environment.

The main Protégé functions are to: load and save OWL and RDF ontologies; edit and visualize classes, properties, and SWRL (Semantic Web Rule Language) rules; define logical class characteristics as

⁶ <http://protege.stanford.edu>

OWL expressions; execute reasoners such as description logic classifiers; and edit OWL individuals for Semantic Web markup.

Protégé is available in different versions, each including different plug-ins, whose main difference is the ontology language that they support:

- Protégé version 3 supports OWL 1.0, RDF(S) and Frames.
- Protégé version 4 supports OWL 2.0.⁷

TopBraid Composer⁸ is another modeling environment for developing Semantic Web ontologies and building semantic applications. It is fully compliant with W3C standards and offers support for developing, managing and testing configurations of knowledge models and their instance knowledge bases. It is implemented as an Eclipse plug-in.

Figure 3 TBC Logo

TopBraid Composer incorporates a flexible and extensible framework with a published API for developing semantic client/server or browser-based solutions that can integrate disparate applications and data sources. TopBraid Composer is a commercial software available in three different versions: Free Edition, Standard Edition and Maestro Edition.

On the whole, this section sketched the essentials of foremost methodologies and technologies for building ontologies. Our main purpose is to select a relevant methodology to design the SatisFactory ontologies, as part of Task 2.2 activities, and a tool to implement this ontology, as part of Task 3.1. Based on the conducted literature review, we have decided to apply the **NeOn** methodology, as it suggests straightforward pathways and activities for building ontology networks. Besides, this methodology supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments. Whereas, the other methodologies (METHONTOLOGY, On-To-Knowledge and DILIGENT) do not provide guidelines for the reuse and re-engineering of existing knowledge resources (ontological and non-ontological). This is a key driver in a context where several product related resources exist, in terms of standards, ontologies, meta-data, glossaries, taxonomies, etc. In terms of tools, we have decided to use **Protégé**, version 4, which supports **OWL 2.0** and its profiles.

2.3 W3C STANDARDS

W3C standards define an Open Web Platform for application development that has the potential to enable developers to build rich interactive experiences, powered by vast data stores, which are available on any device. Although the boundaries of the platform continue to evolve, industry leaders speak nearly in unison about how HTML5 will be the cornerstone for this platform. But the full

⁷ Nowadays Protégé latest version is 5.0 Beta, which obviously still support OWL 2.0

⁸ http://www.topquadrant.com/products/TB_Composer.html

strength of the platform relies on many more technologies that W3C and its partners are creating, including CSS, SVG, WOFF, the Semantic Web stack, XML, and a variety of APIs.

W3C develops these technical specifications and guidelines through a process designed to maximize consensus about the content of a technical report, to ensure high technical and editorial quality, and to earn endorsement by W3C and the broader community⁹.

2.3.1 *Semantic Web*

In addition to the classic “Web of documents” W3C is helping to build a technology stack to support a “Web of data,” the sort of data you find in databases. The ultimate goal of the Web of data is to enable computers to do more useful work and to develop systems that can support trusted interactions over the network. The term “Semantic Web” refers to W3C’s vision of the Web of linked data. Semantic Web technologies enable people to create data stores on the Web, build vocabularies, and write rules for handling data. Linked Data¹⁰ are empowered by technologies such as RDF, SPARQL, OWL, and SKOS.

2.3.2 *Linked Data*

The Semantic Web is a Web of Data — of dates and titles and part numbers and chemical properties and any other data one might conceive of. The collection of Semantic Web technologies (RDF, OWL, SKOS, SPARQL, etc.) provides an environment where application can query that data, draw inferences using vocabularies, and the like.

However, to make the Web of Data a reality, it is important to have the huge amount of data on the Web available in a standard format, reachable and manageable by Semantic Web tools. Furthermore, not only does the Semantic Web need access to data, but *relationships among data* should be made available, too, to create a *Web* of Data (as opposed to a sheer collection of datasets). This collection of interrelated datasets on the Web can also be referred to as Linked Data.

To achieve and create Linked Data, technologies should be available for a common format (RDF), to make either conversion or on-the-fly access to existing databases (relational, XML, HTML, etc.). It is also important to be able to setup query endpoints to access that data more conveniently. W3C provides a palette of technologies (RDF, GRDDL, POWDER, RDFa, the upcoming R2RML, RIF, and SPARQL) to get access to the data.

Linked Data lies at the heart of what Semantic Web is all about: large scale integration of, and reasoning on, data on the Web. Almost all applications listed in, say collection of Semantic Web Case Studies and Use Cases are essentially based on the accessibility of, and integration of Linked Data at various level of complexities.

2.3.3 *Vocabularies*

On the Semantic Web, vocabularies define the concepts and relationships (also referred to as “terms”) used to describe and represent an area of concern. Vocabularies are used to classify the terms that can be used in a particular application, characterize possible relationships, and define

⁹ <http://www.w3.org/standards/>

¹⁰ <http://linkeddata.org/>

possible constraints on using those terms. In practice, vocabularies can be very complex (with several thousands of terms) or very simple (describing one or two concepts only).

There is no clear division between what is referred to as “vocabularies” and “ontologies”. The trend is to use the word “ontology” for more complex, and possibly quite formal collection of terms, whereas “vocabulary” is used when such strict formalism is not necessarily used or only in a very loose sense. Vocabularies are the basic building blocks for inference techniques on the Semantic Web.

The role of vocabularies on the Semantic Web are to help data integration when, for example, ambiguities may exist on the terms used in the different data sets, or when a bit of extra knowledge may lead to the discovery of new relationships. Consider, for example, the application of ontologies in the field of health care. Medical professionals use them to represent knowledge about symptoms, diseases, and treatments. Pharmaceutical companies use them to represent information about drugs, dosages, and allergies. Combining this knowledge from the medical and pharmaceutical communities with patient data enables a whole range of intelligent applications such as decision support tools that search for possible treatments; systems that monitor drug efficacy and possible side effects; and tools that support epidemiological research.

Another type of example is to use vocabularies to organize knowledge. Libraries, museums, newspapers, government portals, enterprises, social networking applications, and other communities that manage large collections of books, historical artefacts, news reports, business glossaries, blog entries, and other items can now use vocabularies, using standard formalisms, to leverage the power of linked data.

It depends on the application how complex vocabularies they use. In some cases it might be decided not to use even small vocabularies, and rely on the logic of the application program. In other cases it might be chosen to use very simple vocabularies like the one described in the examples section below, and let a general Semantic Web environment use that extra information to make the identification of the terms. Finally, some applications may need more complex ontologies with complex reasoning procedures. It all depends on the requirements and the goals of the applications.

To satisfy these different needs, W3C offers a large palette of techniques to describe and define different forms of vocabularies in a standard format. These include RDF and RDF Schemas, Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS), Web Ontology Language (OWL), and the Rule Interchange Format (RIF). The choice among these different technologies depend on the complexity and rigor required by a specific application.

2.3.4 *Query*

In the framework of Semantic Web, the meaning of “query” is related to technologies and protocols that allows information retrieval.

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) provides the foundation for publishing and linking data, then, many technologies allow to embed data in documents, such as RDFa, GRDDL, or expose what is stored in databases, or make it available as RDF files.

The SPARQL has been designed to send queries and receive results, e.g. through HTTP or SOAP, within the Semantic Web, which is typically represented using RDF as a data format. This query language is based on (triples) patterns that are similar to RDF triples, and the results of a SPARQL query will be the resources for all triples that match those patterns. Thus, it provides a powerful tool

that allows to extract complex information (i.e., existing resource references and their relationships) and present them in different friendly format (i.e. tables).

2.3.5 XML Technology

XML Technologies include XML, XML Namespaces, XML Schema, XSLT, Efficient XML Interchange (EXI), and other related standards.

2.3.5.1 XML Essentials

The Extensible Markup Language (XML) is a simple text-based format for representing structured information: documents, data, configuration, books, transactions, invoices, and much more. It was derived from an older standard format called SGML (ISO 8879), in order to be more suitable for Web use.

XML is one of the most widely-used formats for sharing structured information today: between programs, between people, between computers and people, both locally and across networks.

HTML and XML are very similar, however, the syntax rules of XML are strict: XML tools will not process files that contain errors, but instead will give you error messages so that you fix them. This means that almost all XML documents can be processed reliably by computer software.

The main differences from HTML are:

- All elements must be closed or marked as empty.
- Empty elements can be closed as normal, `<happiness></happiness>` or you can use a special short-form, `<happiness />` instead.
- In HTML, you only need to quote an attribute value under certain circumstances (it contains a space, or a character not allowed in a name), but the rules are hard to remember. In XML, attribute values must always be quoted: `<happiness type="joy" />`
- In HTML there is a built-in set of element names (along with their attributes). In XML, there are no built-in names (although names starting with xml have special meanings).
- In HTML, there is a list of some built-in character names like `´` for `é` but XML does not have this. In XML, there are only five built-in character entities: `<`, `>`, `&`, `"` and `'` for `<`, `>`, `&`, `"` and `'` respectively. You can define your own entities in a Document Type Definition, or you can use any Unicode character (see next item).
- In HTML, there are also numeric character references, such as `&` for `&`. You can refer to any Unicode character, but the number is decimal, whereas in the Unicode tables the number is usually in hexadecimal. XML also allows hexadecimal references: `&` for example.

XML has a number of advantages over many other formats. For any particular scenario, you might be able to come up with a better format, but then you would have to include costs of converting and processing your format, and of training, and of the XML-specific editing and searching tool that are now very widely available. Some of the advantages of XML include:

- Redundancy
 - XML markup is very verbose. For example, every end tag must be supplied, such as `</description>` in the example. This lets the computer catch common errors such as incorrect nesting.

- Self-describing
 - The readability of XML (it is a text-based format) and the presence of element and attribute names in XML means that people looking at an XML document can often get a head start on understanding the format (and it also helps people to find mistakes!)
- Network effect and the XML Promise
 - Any XML document can be read and processed by any XML tool whatsoever. Of course, some XML tools might want specific XML markup, but the XML format itself can be read by any XML parser: you can't say, this XML document is only to be processed by such-and-such tool
 - This means that every new XML document increases the value of every other XML document, and of every XML tool, and every new XML tool increases the value of every XML document and hence of every other tool. Today, XML is the most widely-used format of its kind, anywhere in the world.

2.3.5.2 *Efficient Interchange*

The EXI (Efficient XML Interchange) standard improves the performance, network efficiency, and power consumption of XML applications across the full range of use cases. Extensive testing shows that EXI performs consistently better than previous XML formats, data compression, and even packed binary data formats. As such, it brings the full range of XML benefits to even the most demanding applications.

EXI defines a compact encoding of an XML Info set for a wide range of usage scenarios, with a particular attention to keeping the necessary processing under control.

The EXI format uses a hybrid approach drawn from the information and formal language theories, plus practical techniques verified by measurements, for entropy encoding XML information. Using a relatively simple algorithm, which is amenable to fast and compact implementation, and a small set of data type representations, it reliably produces efficient encodings of XML event streams. The grammar production system and format definition of EXI are specified in the EXI Format 1.0 specification.

In addition to the EXI Format, the EXI Profile for limiting usage of dynamic memory is designed to accommodate very constrained devices (micro-controllers, sensors, etc.). In those environments, dynamic memory allocation is inexistent or very limited, therefore the EXI grammar learning mechanism needs to be controlled.

2.3.5.3 *Schema*

Schema languages and, in particular W3C XSD (XML Schema Definitions), are designed to express constraints about the structure of XML documents. In general, a Schema can be used

- to provide a list of elements and attributes in a vocabulary;
- to associate types, such as integer, string, etc., or more specifically such as hat size, sock color, etc., with values found in documents;

- to constrain where elements and attributes can appear, and what can appear inside those elements, such as saying that a chapter title occurs inside a chapter, and that a chapter must consist of a chapter title followed by one or more paragraphs of text;
- to provide documentation that is both human-readable and machine-processable;
- to give a formal description of one or more documents.

Information in schema documents is often used by XML-aware editing systems so that they can offer users the most likely elements to occur at any given location in a document. Checking a document against a Schema is known as Validating against that schema. Validating against a schema is an important component of quality assurance.

Since XSD supports associating data types with element and attribute content, it is also used for data binding, that is, for software components that read and write XML representations of computer programming-language objects.

2.3.5.4 Transformation

XSLT and XSL-FO are W3C Recommendations for defining XML document transformation and presentation. Use XSLT to transform documents into XSL-FO for printing or viewing; you can also use XSLT as a general XML-aware programming and transformation language, and you can use XSL-FO directly without XSLT.

A typical application might be taking groups of XML documents to PDF:

Figure 4 From XSLT Transformation

XSL Transformations (XSLT 2.0) is a language for transforming XML documents into other XML documents, text documents or HTML documents. You might want to format a chapter of a book using XSL-FO, or you might want to take a database query and format it as HTML.

With XSLT 2.0, processors can operate not only on XML but on anything that can be made to look like XML: relational database tables, geographical information systems, file systems, anything from which your XSLT processor can build an XDM instance. In some cases an XSLT 2.0 processor might also be able to work directly from a database of XDM instances. This ability to operate on multiple input files in multiple formats, and to treat them all as if they were XML files, is very powerful. It is shared with XQuery, and with anything else using XPath 2.0:

Figure 5 From XML documents merging

XSLT has become the language of choice for a very wide range of XML applications. It is of course still used to produce XSL-FO documents for printing, but it is also used to integrate back-end software for web sites. You will find XSLT inside most modern web browsers, so that XML can be transformed on the fly without the user even noticing. You will also find XSLT on the desktop, in servers, in network appliances, and forming a basic and dependable part of computer infrastructure almost everywhere you look.

3. ONTOLOGY DESIGN

METHONTOLOGY, On-To-Knowledge, and DILIGENT were till 2009 the most often mentioned methodologies serving to build ontologies. They mainly refer to guidelines for single ontology construction varying from ontology specification to ontology implementation; ontology researchers are usually targeting them. On the other hand, a quite new methodology (2010), the NeOn Methodology, suggests pathways and activities for different scenarios, instead of prescribing a rigid workflow.

Most of the aforementioned methodologies assume that ontologies have to be built first, then XSD schemas will be generated during the next designing phases and according to the KBs structure. In our case, the Satisfactory Semantic Context Manager (SCM) aims on the one hand to enrich semantically the CIDEM, on the other hand it aims to support specific Application Scenarios by developing a semantic environment to store and manage specific knowledge. The latter case doesn't introduce any new modelling issue and can be tackled canonically by leveraging the above mentioned technique. Now on, we will refer to this standard modelling approach as a top-down one. The first case, instead, introduces a non-trivial modelling feature for the SCM. The knowledge-base (KB) developed to reason on semantic data, which are shared through the system according to pre-defined XSD schemas, has to be built according to an "opposite" approach (approach).

Figure 6 Semantic lifting of XML Schemas

Thus, the design and development of the SCM imply the hybrid adoption of those two parallel approaches (top-down and bottom-up) and lead to a layered, and linked as well, semantic environment.

For the purposes of T2.2 the above mentioned NEON methodology has been adopted, hence, it will be further described in the following section. Before this modelling methodology is introduced, few information about the general design of the SCM are given.

In general, the Semantic Environment strength relies on its network. Within the Satisfactory platform, this network should links together different nature ontologies and aims to provide a common vocabulary. In the next section, we will described how it's possible to further enrich the semantic environment by linking it with other existing ontologies (NEON methodology, scenario 5 and 6), in order to provide, on one hand, a general vocabulary of classes and predicates for describing domain ontologies, with the specific aim of promoting interoperability with external datasets and domains. On the other hand, it provides a coherent framework of broad subjects and

Figure 8 Three level SCM structure

3.1 **NEON METHODOLOGY**

The NeOn Methodology [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa, 2010] for the construction of ontology networks is “a scenario-based methodology that supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments”. The key assets of the NeOn Methodology are:

- A set of nine scenarios for the construction of ontologies and ontology networks, focusing on the reuse of ontological and non-ontological resources, the reengineering and merging, and counting a lot on dynamism and collaboration.
- The NeOn Glossary of Processes and Activities defines the processes and activities carried out, when teams build jointly ontology networks.
- Methodological guidelines for a variety of processes and activities of the ontology network development process, such as the reuse and reengineering of ontological and non-ontological resources, the ontology requirements specification, the ontology localization, the scheduling, etc. All processes and activities are described with (a) a filling card, (b) a workflow, and (c) examples.

The nine scenarios for ontologies and ontology networks creation can be briefly presented below:

Scenario 1: From specification to implementation. The ontology network is created from zero (without reusing existing resources). Ontology requirements are specified by developers [M. Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2009]. Later, it is suggested that a search for potential resources to be reused is conducted, in order to finally carry out the scheduling activity, so that developers are enabled to follow the plan for the development of the ontology network.

Scenario 2: Reusing and re-engineering non-ontological resources (NORs). Developers should carry out the NOR reuse process for deciding, according to the ontology requirements, which NORs can be reused to build the ontology network. Then, the selected NORs should be re-engineered into ontologies [B. Villazón-Terrazas et al., 2010].

Scenario 3: Reusing ontological resources. Developers use ontological resources (ontologies as a whole, ontology modules, and/or ontology statements) to build ontology networks.

Scenario 4: Reusing and re-engineering ontological resources. Ontology developers reuse and re-engineer ontological resources.

Scenario 5: Reusing and merging ontological resources. This scenario arises when several ontological re-sources in the same domain are selected for reuse and developers wish to create a new ontological resource with the selected resources.

Scenario 6: Reusing, merging and re-engineering ontological resources. Ontology developers reuse, merge, and re-engineer ontological resources. This scenario looks similar to Scenario 5, but here developers decide to re-engineer the set of merged resources.

Scenario 7: Reusing ontology design patterns (ODPs). Ontology developers access repositories (e.g., <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/>) to reuse ODPs.

Scenario 8: Restructuring ontological resources. Ontology developers restructure (e.g., modularize, prune, ex-tend, and/or specialize) ontological resources to be integrated in the ontology network.

Scenario 9: Localizing ontological resources. Ontology developers adapt an ontology to other languages and culture communities, thus obtaining a multilingual ontology [M. Espinoza et al., 2009].

For the purpose of this work we recognized the need for analysis and exploitation of the first three NeOn scenarios as described above. Later in this document we describe the creation of Satisfactory ontologies from scratch (Scenario 1), the transformation of non-ontological resources to Satisfactory ontologies (Scenario 2) and finally the reuse of already existing ontological resources such as the Human Resources Management ontology network and the Context Management Ontologies.

In the framework of the first scenario, Ontology Requirements Specification, which is the activity of collecting the requirements that the ontology should fulfill, has been repeatedly performed with all interested parties. The output of this important activity is the ontology requirements specification document (ORSD), which includes the purpose, the level of formality and scope of each ontology, the target group and the intended uses of the ontology, as well as a set of requirements, which are those needs that the ontology to be built should cover. The complete list of ORSDs can be retrieved within the ANNEX 1.

Therefore, Figure 8 gives the big picture about the Semantic Context Manager (SCM) ontologies network by classifying them according to the three aforementioned levels. In the next sections, instead, we aim to describe all the ontological models according with the NEON classification and together with their requirement specification analysis. It's worth pointing out that such analyses are non-trivial and play an important role in defining the edges of the Knowledge-Base, the granularity and the required degree of detail.

3.2 SCENARIO 1 ONTOLOGIES

The so-called "Scenario 1 Ontologies" are all those semantic models that are built without reusing other ontological resources, and then developed from scratch. Within the Satisfactory framework such models are basically focused on specific contexts, e.g. one model for each BSC, which has its

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own vocabulary and structure. Thus, in this section we give a brief description of the Business Scenarios that should potentially exploit the Semantic Context Manager, moreover, we aim to describe what concepts are relevant in terms of piece of knowledge forming the whole BSC Knowledge Base.

The first two BSCs are concerning CERTH shop floor. Hence, according with the template (Table 2), and within T2.2, CERTH produced an ORSD in order to analyse the role of ontologies within their shop floor. The whole document can be seen in the ANNEX 1.1.

Table 1 ORSD template

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT	
1	Purpose (The general goal of the ontology. In other words, the main function or role that the ontology should have.)
2	Scope (The general coverage and the degree of detail that the ontology should have.)
3	Implementation Language (The formal language that the ontology should have.)
4	Intended End-Users (The intended end-users expected for the ontology.)
5	Intended Uses (The intended uses expected for the ontology.)
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non- Functional Requirements (General attributes and aspects, like terminology, qualities, and conventions, which are not related to the ontology’s principal content and the ontology should anyway try to respect. It may be written in natural language.)
	b. Functional Requirements (Must-have characteristics and specific functions which can manifest during the application. It may be useful to write it in the form of questions and associated answers.)

3.2.1 BSC-5 Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants for chemical processes (CERTH)

The following business scenario is taken from the daily needs of a semi industrial environment. This is the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. There are several pilot plants with different procedures and functions within the shop floor. These pilot plants consist of many complicated components performing several procedures [D1.2].

There are three Application Scenarios involved that cover a subset of activities that are performed on daily basis at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI:

- BSC-5.1 Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction
- BSC-5.2 Start-up procedures of a Hydro cracking pilot plant

- BSC-5.3 Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures

However, the BSC (Business Scenario) is investigated as a whole. This because all the related application scenarios share most of the concepts and knowledge sources. Through the analysis of the BSC description (see D1.2) and the ORSD, the Ontology Engineer is able to see at a glance all the concepts that are involved within this context, which constitutes the worker’s knowledge. The main set of concepts (classes) recognized is included in the following table (Table 2):

Table 2 BSC5 concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supervisors and Managers • Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Procedure</i>	Planned activity to perform within the pilot plant
<i>Data</i>	Information data, can be either static or dynamic (often called “functions”)
<i>Component</i>	Simple component of the pilot plant
<i>Physical Asset</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the worker toward the completion of a specific procedure

, and their respective relations. Figure 9 gives an overview of the ontology model.

Figure 9 BSC5 Ontology

3.2.2 BSC-6 Recognition of accidents and path optimization for workers' movement (CERTH)

The BSC-6 is primarily focused on the safety of the workers. This because the extent of CPERI's pilot plants and the plethora of the necessary daily procedures impose numerous workers to spend most of their working time within high risk shop floor area [D1.2].

In particular, the only Application Scenario (BSC 6.1) refers to movement at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. The purpose of this Application Scenario is to reduce the number of accidents and to give optimal paths to workers moving inside the shop floor.

In this case, the knowledge of the worker should be mostly based on location recognition concepts, such as:

Table 3 BSC6 concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot Plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Area</i>	Accessible or Forbidden Area
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the user

Figure 10 BSC6 Ontology

3.2.3 Development of “on Job” training/educational environment

The Training and Educational Platform is designed within the task T2.5 led by REGOLA on the basis of tasks T1.1 and T1.3 and further enriched through the application of semantic techniques developed by EPFL. This SatisFactory component aims to provide a common vocabulary that supports the training activities within the shop floor. It’s worth emphasizing that the training/education will be performed “on job”. This means that the worker will receive useful information while performing standard activities according to his profile characteristics, such as *experience*, *skills*, and the like. These information are, then, enriched by context knowledge and provided to the end user as the result of different kind of system querying, for instance:

- Off-line information request
- On special event triggered request

Therefore, according to the ORSD document produced by REGOLA for this task (see Annex 1.3), the following set of concepts have been identified:

Table 4 Training Platform concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Foremen, Coordinators and Process operators
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by an user and characterized by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Interval

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting State • Final State
<i>Tool</i>	<p>Set of available tools, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HDMI • AR device • Instrument
<i>Factory Area</i>	<p>Area of the shop floor where a specific action is taking place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work Station • Office • Other
<i>Personal Detail</i>	<p>User details such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience • Name • ID • Age • Skill
<i>Machine</i>	<p>Physical asset which the worker uses to perform an activity</p>
<i>Experience Level</i>	<p>Taxonomy of different level of experience that can be achieved by the worker or required from a specific machine use.</p>
<i>Ergonomic Recommendation</i>	<p>Safety aspects related to an activity performed on a machine.</p>
<i>Activity</i>	<p>Concepts related to an activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description • Duration • Level • Type <p>All those concepts are modelled as single classes. Further explanations will be given on D3.1.</p>

Thus, an excerpt of the ontology structure is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Training Platform ontology

3.3 SCENARIO 2 ONTOLOGIES

The Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) is defined according to XML schemas designed for different specific domains within the task T1.4. According to these schemas, which basically define a list of elements and attributes in a vocabulary, it's possible to apply the aforementioned bottom-up approach and build ontologies that provide a semantic representation of the related domain knowledge and fix as well the lack of support for reasoning.

In this first version of D2.2, we present two XSD to OWL “semantic liftings” in order to give a preliminary overview of the methodology applied to the 2nd scenario ontologies.

Basically all the schemas are translated manually through the application of a stepwise process described as follow:

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1. The XML Schema give as input (XSD) is analysed
2. We build an XML- Schema Graph (XSG) that describes the schema in the same way whatever its design style is. An XSG is basically composed of a vertex set, and an edge set. The vertex set contains all elements, attributes, non-primitive types, element groups and attribute groups. The edge set contains the edges established:
 - a. From each element to its type (if not primitive),
 - b. From each type, element group or attribute group to their contained elements and/or attributes.

This phase is not visible, we focus on the final product, i.e. the ontology.

3. Given the XSG as input, we generate OWL entities. Basically, OWL Classes emerge from complex types, element group declarations, and attribute-group declarations according to sets of rules that will be further discussed in the next version.

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```
<xs:element name="bibliography">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" ref="biblioentry"/>
    </xs:sequence>
    <xs:attribute name="id" use="required" type="xs:NCName"/>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="biblioentry">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" ref="author"/>
      <xs:element ref="title"/>
      <xs:element ref="publisher"/>
      <xs:element ref="pubdate"/>
    </xs:sequence>
    <xs:attribute name="id" use="required" type="xs:NCName"/>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="author">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element ref="firstname"/>
      <xs:element minOccurs="0" ref="othername"/>
      <xs:element ref="surname"/>
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="firstname" type="xs:NCName"/>
<xs:element name="othername" type="xs:NCName"/>
<xs:element name="surname" type="xs:NCName"/>
<xs:element name="title" type="xs:string"/>
<xs:element name="publisher">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element ref="publishername"/>
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="publishername" type="xs:string"/>
<xs:element name="pubdate" type="xs:integer"/>
</xs:schema>
```

1

2

3

Figure 12 from XSD to OWL

3.3.1 R3D

R3D is the Online Real-time Standard Operating Procedure Model. This model is serialized as an XML schema. It's important to point out that this model is deeply based on a "linked resources" approach. Thus lot information are maintained not directly into XML, but are represented by the linked data (e.g. 3D model, images, animation, etc.). It has been used as base SOP model to implement an AR-based system, to support assembly step of critical components for plants. It represents a core component of the software architecture designed by Regola, on which a lot of software modules, provided for Satisfactory, will be based. It represents one of the most effective choices, in order to maximize the results of the software components that Regola will provide to Satisfactory.

Figure 13 shows an excerpt of the R3D ontology that has been designed to semantically lift the R3D XML-schema and support the on-job training and educational activities performed within the shop floor. Following Table 5 show the set of *Classes* and *Object Relations* that represent the structure of this ontology

Table 5 R3D Ontology: Classes and Object properties

Classes	Object Property	Domain	Range
action	hasAction	step	action
description_layer	hasDescriptionLayer	description_layers	description_layer
description_layers	hasObjectldO	objects	objectid
inventory	hasObjectldO	objects_to	objectid
nodes	hasObjectldO	objects_with	objectid
objectid	hasOperation	nodes	operation
objects	hasRelation	relations	relation
objects_to	hasStep	operation	step
objects_with	hasWarehouseElement	inventory	warehouse_element
operation	involvesInventory	procedure	inventory
procedure	involvesNodes	procedure	nodes
relation	involvesRelations	procedure	relations
relations	isDescribedByDescriptionLayer	action	description_layers
step	isDescribedByObjects	action	objects
warehouse_element	isDescribedByObjectsTo	action	objects_to
	isDescribedByObjectsWith	action	objects_with

In the Annex 2.2 a description of 60 designed *Data Properties* is shown in a table

Figure 13 R3D Ontology

3.3.2 B2MML

B2MML is an XML implementation of the ANSI/ISA-95, Enterprise-Control System Integration, family of standards (ISA-95), known internationally as IEC/ISO 62264. B2MML consists of a set of XML schemas written using the World Wide Web Consortium's XML Schema language (XSD) that implement the data models in the ISA-95 standard.

This ontology is so far the biggest one and required a lot of effort to be modelled. At the end of its designing phase, we could define *96 concepts* and *189 relations*, which are presented in detail within the Annex 2.1. Therefore, it's taught to present an image that shows the whole B2MML ontology. Next two images (Figures 14 and 15) show the so-called neighbourhood of two important concepts of the B2MML vocabulary, such as *Physical Asset*, *Equipment*.

3.4 SCENARIO 3 ONTOLOGIES

3.4.1 Human Resources Management Ontology

The Human Resources Management Ontology, acts as a common "language" in the form of a set of controlled vocabularies to describe the details of human resources management. The ontology was developed following the NeOn Methodology for Building Ontology Networks and with the ontology engineering tools WSMT and WebODE. The Ontology is open source. The HRM ontology is available for download in WSML or in RDF.

The ontology is composed of thirteen modular ontologies: Competence, Compensation, Driving License, Economic Activity, Education, Geography, Job Offer, Job Seeker, Labour Regulatory, Language, Occupation, Skill and Time. The main sub-ontologies are the Job Offer and Job Seeker, which are intended to represent the structure of a job posting and a CV respectively. While these two sub-ontologies were built taking as a starting point some HR-XML recommendations, the other sub-ontologies were derived from some available international standards (like NACE, ISCO-88 (COM), FOET, etc.), Employment Services classifications and international codes (like ISO 3166, ISO 6392, etc.) that best fit the European requirements. The figure below presents these thirteen modular ontologies (each ontology is represented by a triangle). Ten of them were obtained after wrapping the original format of the standard/classification, using ad hoc translator or wrapper for each standard/classification.¹²

¹² <http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/index.php/en/ontologies/99-hrmontology>

Figure 17 Context Management Ontology Network

4. ONTOLOGY EXPLOITATION

Besides being a cornerstone for defining a knowledge domain, the Satisfactory Network of Ontologies will interact with several SatisFactory components. In the following section, we outline how the Network of Ontologies will be exploited.

4.1 *KNOWLEDGE VISUALIZATION*

The Ontology captures knowledge that exists in the domain. This implicit and explicit knowledge is of great value for people who are trying to understand the domain. By visualizing the ontology, this knowledge may become much easier to understand. The knowledge can be visualized as a graph. The nodes of this graph can show the different concepts in the domain of interest and edges can demonstrate the various relations between concepts. In this way, the several interested parties can navigate through domain knowledge and come into conclusion regarding the nature of their problem (or simple question) more easily.

Some tools have already been developed towards this direction, but they lack user friendliness and expressivity. Well known examples are OntoViz and OntoGraph, plug-ins for Protégé ontology editor. More advanced cutting edge solutions focus more on the visualization tools. Such tools become more powerful by including more expressivity to existing graph representation techniques. A big challenge in this field is how to include more knowledge elements in one single frame and at the same time keep the picture simple enough as to be understood. An example of the before mentioned tools is included in the Open Semantic Framework (OSF). The OSF brings together several semantic technologies to create a software stack where the Ontology plays the role of the brain.

A customized solution for the needs of SatisFactory project should focus on solving problems of common understanding between different partners in the design and manufacturing domain. Going a step further, the solution should provide a way to complete knowledge gaps in a visual way by revealing knowledge that was previously unlinked and hidden.

4.2 *DATA INTEGRATION*

The application of the Linked Data principles for data integration, created and maintained in order to explore the shop floor knowledge, appears to be an added value for SatisFactory. One of the key benefits of Semantic Web technologies, as key enablers of Linked Data, is the creation of data stores using URIs for identifying resources and their relations.

4.3 *RULES INFERENCE*

Ontology as a domain modelling technique assumes existence of rules that express logic in relation co-dependencies. To clarify this concept we will use a simple example. In a case of ontology

modelling a domain of car-ownership might have simple rules such as "Tom owns X car" and "X is a German factory". In that case, rule inference will provide us a new knowledge saying "Tom owns German car". Rule inference engines do this automatically and can chain more than two rules and thus, provide us with more complex conclusions, resulting in more detail, clearer model of the domain.

For example, in the case of DSS application ontology, rules are created so that they enable managers to conduct specific assessments. Regarding the Training Platform, instead, triggered requests and off-line support involve the definition of reasoning rules in order to exploit the shop floor knowledge to analyse and improve the training activities.

It is important to highlight that rule inference is self-initiated process. It is a background process on all levels for all the concepts, every time that ontology is edited or the set of rules is extended. End-users do not even need to be familiar with these processes. Inference results are expressed through wider range of allowed queries for knowledge. Under certain constrains embedded in graphical interface, user can ask a direct questions and be presented with an answer as long as the answer is reachable using rule chaining.

4.4 CONTEXT-DRIVEN INFORMATION ACQUISITION

Context is defined as any information that can be used to characterize the situation of an entity [A. Zimmermann et al., 2007]. In the context of SatisFactory, the ontology will enable retrieving contextual relationships behind an entity. An entity is a person, place, or object that is considered relevant to the interaction between the user and an application. Thus, SatisFactory sensors should provide sets of shop floor information data that can be exploited in order to extract context-driven knowledge through the application of rules, and then derive the relevancy of those elements in specific situations.

Figure 18 illustrates an example of Shop floor and Management views. This example has been extracted from LinkedDesign and gives a practical idea of context-driven info exploitation. From a management perspective, information such as part costs of a critical disturbance status of the part is relevant. Whereas, from a shop floor perspectives, different information related to the same part can be derived such as failure rate or critical failure status.

Figure 18 Example of Mock-ups based on context-driven information acquisition mechanisms

4.5 ALIGNMENT WITH EXISTING ONTOLOGICAL RESOURCES

A key benefit of semantic technologies is the possibility to adopt and extend existing ontological resources and meta-data initiatives being standards-based, bridging thus multiple domains specific knowledge: environmental, mechatronic, etc. Ontology alignment consists of the identification if the concepts belonging to the to-be-matched pairs of ontologies are related to each other via a *sub-concept* or an *equivalence* relationship.

An initial work in terms of manual alignment should be conducted in collaboration with Atlantis and Regola, as part of T2.5 and T3.5, in order to align the **SCM Ontology** with an existing ontology modeling the domain of features-based product design [S. Abdul Ghafour , 2009]. For instance, Figure 19 illustrates an example of the network ontology resulting in alignment with ontological resources. Further details will be given in the next section.

Figure 19 Example of a network ontology through alignment

Therefore, as already introduced in Section 4, a wide ontology network (we can refer to it as an Upper Level Ontology) may be obtained by linking, and then reusing, existing ontologies in order to enrich the SCM.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this first version of the deliverable regarding Knowledge modelling for human resource optimization, we present the background Knowledge Management Engineering techniques, modelling methodologies and standards that will be leveraged by the Semantic Context Manager (SCM) in order to support SatisFactory functionalities.

By focusing on Neon methodology for Ontology engineering and in particular on the first three scenarios proposed by the latter, this document presents a hybrid approach that leads to the creation of the SatisFactory network of ontologies which capture the explicit and implicit shop floor knowledge.

As part of Scenario 1 the presented semantic models, which are created from scratch, aim to model the concepts and relations of two business scenarios proposed by CERTH/CPERI and related to the in-lab shop floor selected as the first pilot. Moreover, we present an ontological model developed from scratch as well which aims to support the on Job training and educational platform. Within Scenario 2, we present already existing non-ontological resources (XML Schemas) and we perform the necessary transformations (semantic lifting) in order to enrich those resources and create the ontologies that support R3D (training activities) and B2MML (manufacturing processes). Finally, we introduce the Human Resources and Context Management ontology networks which are aligned to the principal of reusing ontological resources as described by the 3rd Scenario.

The use of the semantic models in SatisFactory is presented through a number of exploitation scenarios. These scenarios include knowledge visualization, data integration, rule-based inference, context-driven information acquisition and alignment with existing ontological resources. Through the use of those exploitation alternatives we aim to assist the deployment phase, which will be the subject of the next deliverable D3.1 Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations.

In conclusion, this deliverable is the first version of the knowledge model for human resource optimization that documents the effort spent during the first 12 months of the project and represents the actual status of the activities in Task 2.2 . The models presented in this document should be perceived as a living asset that will grow while SatisFactory project continues toward its later stages.

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ANNEX –

A1.1 ORSD CERTH/CPERI

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT - CERTH/CPERI	
1	Purpose
	The purpose of creating an ontology within the shop floor is to increase the utilization and accuracy of the information derived by the processes and systems in order to improve collaboration and sharing of knowledge.
2	Scope
	The scope of the ontology is to use data and information from existing and new structures within the shop floor and increase safety, controllability and performance of scheduled or unplanned actions and procedures in an online or offline manner.
3	Implementation Language
	The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool.
4	Intended End-Users
	User 1. Supervisors and Managers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floor Manager • Process Supervisor • Maintenance Manager • Maintenance Supervisor User 2. Operators and Technicians <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Operator • Process Technician • Control, Automation, IT Technician • Electrical Technician
5	Intended Uses
	Use 1. Enhance the decision support and prioritization of actions based on online operation status Use 2. Analyze historical data to derive patterns of behavior and correlations at the process units Use 3. Receive selected subset of online data from the automation systems (I/O field network) of the process units Use 4. Optimize the time to inform involved workers about a potential problem/status of the involved systems Use 5. Organize the operation and maintenance (corrective, preventive) procedures into a

	structured and uniform way
6	Ontology Requirements
	<p>a. Non-Functional Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users misunderstanding shall be reduced. • The healthiness of work shall be increased. • The system should solve problems, not add them. Thus, it should be human and machine understandable, as well as user friendly. • Workers flexibility shall not be inferred. • The system shall integrate with existing collaboration platforms. • Standards procedures documentation shall be accessible and easily handled by non-experienced employees.
	<p>b. Functional Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the ontology help the improvement of the procedures? The system shall allow the time validation of performed actions. This would help the improvement of the procedures and would eventually save a lot of working time. • What kind of information might be exchanged among the involved actors? The system shall enable information exchange and online status monitoring for each workers. • Should the ontology include different workday schedules? The system shall manage both ordinary and extraordinary workday schedules. • Does the ontology take the alarms into consideration? The number of false alarms shall be reduced. The latter does not directly apply to the ontology but this information can be consumed within the ontology in any case. • What kind of information concerning the process should be included within the ontology? The system shall visualize the mapping of the process that is implemented in the unit onto the unit's components, e.g. it shall augment what pipes are currently in use and what kind of gas flows in each of them. • Should the system support maintenance actions? Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be accessed via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action. • Should the system include information concerning personal protection equipment? All actions within the shop floor must be performed with the necessary safety measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be taken according to the performed action. • Should the ontology include smart devices (e.g., computers, tablets, smart glasses, sensors)? The system architecture shall incorporate tablet PCs, several kinds of sensors. • Should the system record the generic situation information? Plenty of information regarding the worker activities which are performed at the shop floor and the respective time-schedule combined with prioritization and criticality information will be consumed by the ontology. • Should the system monitor the shop floor status? Information regarding the status monitoring will be consumed by the ontology. The status monitoring system will provide all necessary information about the status of the shop floor to all actors. • Should different kind of training procedures be provided? Video or audio recorded procedures could be available for new operators and technicians.

A1.2 ORSD TRAINING/EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT – Training Platform	
1	Purpose
<p>The purpose of implementing an ontology to support the Training (On-Job) Educational Platform is to enrich the information concerning the training activities with context aware knowledge.</p>	
2	Scope
<p>The training and Education Platform has the responsibility to provide dedicated services to support the activities of training and education not only to workers and machinery operators but also to manufacturing process supervisor.</p> <p>The scope of the ontology is to allow an automatic system, to interpret and properly manage resources, such as information related to shop floor operations, in order to support the so called On-Job Training.</p>	
3	Implementation Language
<p>The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool by leveraging W3C standard languages such as OWL and RDF.</p>	
4	Intended End-Users

	User 1. Foremen and coordinators User 2. Process operators
5	Intended Uses
	Use 1. Generate a structure of big data covering shop floor activities Use 2. Enhance the communication network between humans and machines Use 3. Collect knowledge within the shop floor Use 4. Support and facilitate training activities
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non-Functional Requirements
	The system should allow humans and machines performances assessment. The system should solve problems, not add them. Thus, it should be human and machine understandable, as well as user-friendly. The system requires a quite powerful central hub collecting and computing real-time data. The system should allow clarity and transparency of information and communication.
	b. Functional Requirements
	The system should extract knowledge from the following original sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Images (e.g. , photos, digital images, etc...) • Models 2D and 3D • Audio Clip/Video • Information provided in formats typically documentary (e.g. , PDF, Doc, PowerPoint, etc...) <p><i>The system should provide (and distinguish) three different semantic categories:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural • Functional • Interaction

A1.3 ORSD INTEGRATED DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT – Training Platform	
1	Purpose
	<p>The purpose of building a Semantic Manager for Integrated DSS within the SatisFactory framework is to ease the integration, reasoning of structured and unstructured information data that flows between different data sources.</p>
2	Scope
	<p>Integrated Decision Support System is responsible for providing feedback to the decision makers regarding immediate or with lower priority actions needed in response to shop floor incidents, together with changes to manufacturing operations and processes and also maintenance operations and schedules.</p> <p>The Ontology Manager aims to enrich the Integrated DSS information flow through context-aware knowledge.</p>
3	Implementation Language
	<p>The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool by leveraging W3C standard languages such as OWL and RDF.</p>
4	Intended End-Users
	<p>User 1. Decision Support System User 2. Knowledge Engineer User 3. Maintenance Manager, who wants to get quick overview upon a KBE solution, or Reports User 4. Production Manager, who wants to get quick overview upon a solution, concerning production line procedures</p>

	User 5. Operational Supervisor
5	Intended Uses
	<p>Use 1. Provide a common and well-defined vocabulary for the SatisFactory platform</p> <p>Use 2. Capture the implicit and explicit knowledge regarding manufacturing processes and operations, maintenance schedules and procedures, production plans and details, worker activities and availability.</p> <p>Use 3. Provide a set of rules for reasoning and inferencing information.</p> <p>Use 4. Set up SPARQL endpoint, which will return RDF triples of de-referenceable URI's, in order to support and facilitate decision making process.</p> <p>Use 5. Interlink with pre-existing vocabularies for maximizing interoperability and re-usability.</p>
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non-Functional Requirements
	<p>The SCM should ease the decision making processed</p> <p>The system should require a dedicated repository</p> <p>The system should provide semantically enriched information data</p> <p>The system should require real-time data, for matters of speed and performance</p>
	b. Functional Requirements
	<p>Is a parameter/variable outside of the predefined normal operation boundaries?</p> <p>Has the parameter/variable surpassed the upper or lower limit of the normal operation boundaries?</p> <p>Where does the parameter/variable surpassing the normal operation boundaries come from?</p> <p>Which part of the plant/procedure, from which sensor?</p> <p>In which shop floor area there is an alarm for a high possibility for an accident?</p> <p>Who has access to the shop floor area where an alarm for a high possibility for an accident has been signaled?</p> <p>What safety procedure is followed for the certain accident type at the certain shop floor area?</p> <p>There is a need to change the production procedures from which product A to which product B?</p> <p>What is the standard operating procedure for terminating the production of product A?</p> <p>What is the standard operating procedure for initiating the production of product B?</p> <p>Is the Preventive Maintenance Schedule available?</p> <p>What resources and tools are needed to implement the Preventive Maintenance Schedule?</p> <p>What is the failure code/report/type?</p> <p>Where is the failure reported?</p>

A2.1 B2MML ONTOLOGY – MODELLING DETAILS

Class
Description
DescriptionType
Equipment
EquipmentAssetMapping
EquipmentAssetMappingType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType
EquipmentClass
EquipmentClassID
EquipmentClassIDType
EquipmentClassProperty
EquipmentClassPropertyType
EquipmentClassType
EquipmentID
EquipmentIDType
EquipmentInformation
EquipmentInformationType
EquipmentLevel
EquipmentProperty
EquipmentPropertyType
EquipmentType
FixedAssetID
HierarchyScope
HierarchyScopeType
ID
IdentifierType
Location
LocationType
Manufacturer
Name
NameType
Person
PersonID

PersonIDType
PersonName
PersonNameType
PersonProperty
PersonPropertyType
PersonType
PersonnelClass
PersonnelClassID
PersonnelClassIDType
PersonnelClassProperty
PersonnelClassPropertyType
PersonnelClassType
PersonnelInformation
PersonnelInformationType
PhysicalAsset
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType
PhysicalAssetClass
PhysicalAssetClassID
PhysicalAssetClassIDType
PhysicalAssetClassProperty
PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
PhysicalAssetClassType
PhysicalAssetID
PhysicalAssetIDType
PhysicalAssetInformation
PhysicalAssetInformationType
PhysicalAssetProperty
PhysicalAssetPropertyType
PhysicalAssetType
PhysicalLocation
ProcessSegmentInformation
PropertyID
PropertyIDType
PublishedDate
PublishedDateType
QualificationTestSpecification

QualificationTestSpecificationID
QualificationTestSpecificationIDType
QualificationTestSpecificationType
TestResult
TestResultType
TestedEquipmentClassProperty
TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType
TestedEquipmentProperty
TestedEquipmentPropertyType
TestedPersonProperty
TestedPersonPropertyType
TestedPersonnelClassProperty
TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType
TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty
TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
TestedPhysicalAssetProperty
TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType
Value
ValueType
VendorID
Version
VersionType

Object Property	Domain	Range
hasDescription	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentClassPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentClassType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentInformationType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentType	Description
hasDescription	PersonPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PersonType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelClassPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelClassType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelInformationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	Description

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	ype	
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetClassType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetInformationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetType	Description
hasDescription	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Description
hasEquipment	EquipmentInformationType	Equipment
hasEquipmentAssetMapping	EquipmentType	EquipmentAssetMapping
hasEquipmentAssetMapping	PhysicalAssetType	EquipmentAssetMapping
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification	EquipmentInformationType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentClass	EquipmentInformationType	EquipmentType
hasEquipmentClassID	EquipmentType	EquipmentClassID
hasEquipmentClassID	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassID
hasEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassProperty
hasEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentClassProperty
hasEquipmentID	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentID	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentID	TestedEquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentLevel	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentLevel	EquipmentType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentLevel	PhysicalAssetType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentProperty	EquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentProperty
hasEquipmentProperty	EquipmentType	EquipmentProperty
hasFixedAssetID	PhysicalAssetType	FixedAssetID
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentInformationType	HierarchyScope

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hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonnelClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonnelInformationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetInformationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	QualificationTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope
hasID	EquipmentClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	EquipmentInformationType	ID
hasID	EquipmentPropertyType	ID
hasID	EquipmentType	ID
hasID	PersonPropertyType	ID
hasID	PersonType	ID
hasID	PersonnelClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	PersonnelClassType	ID
hasID	PersonnelInformationType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetClassType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetInformationType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetType	ID
hasID	QualificationTestSpecificationType	ID
hasLocation	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentClassType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentInformationType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentType	Location
hasLocation	PersonType	Location
hasLocation	PersonnelClassType	Location
hasLocation	PersonnelInformationType	Location
hasLocation	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Location
hasManufacturer	PhysicalAssetClassType	Manufacturer

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hasName	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Name
hasName	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Name
hasPerson	PersonnelInformationType	Person
hasPersonID	PersonnelClassType	PersonID
hasPersonID	TestedPersonPropertyType	PersonID
hasPersonName	PersonType	PersonName
hasPersonProperty	PersonPropertyType	PersonProperty
hasPersonProperty	PersonType	PersonProperty
hasPersonnelClass	PersonnelInformationType	PersonnelClassType
hasPersonnelClassID	PersonType	PersonnelClassID
hasPersonnelClassID	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassID
hasPersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassProperty
hasPersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassType	PersonnelClassProperty
hasPhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAsset
hasPhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAsset
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetClass	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetClass
hasPhysicalAssetClassID	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetClassID
hasPhysicalAssetClassID	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassID
hasPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasPhysicalAssetID	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetID
hasPhysicalAssetID	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetID
hasPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetProperty
hasPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetProperty

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hasPhysicalLocation	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalLocation
hasPropertyID	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedEquipmentPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPersonPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPublishedDate	EquipmentInformationType	PublishedDate
hasPublishedDate	PersonnelInformationType	PublishedDate
hasPublishedDate	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PublishedDate
hasQualificationTestSpecification	PersonnelInformationType	QualificationTestSpecificationType
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonPropertyType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonnelClassPropertyType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonnelClassType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasTestResult	EquipmentClassType	TestResult
hasTestResult	EquipmentPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestResult	PersonPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestResult	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestedEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedEquipmentClassProperty
hasTestedEquipmentProperty	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedEquipmentProperty
hasTestedPersonProperty	QualificationTestSpecificationType	TestedPersonProperty
hasTestedPersonnelClassProperty	QualificationTestSpecificationType	TestedPersonnelClassProperty
hasTestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasTestedPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedPhysicalAssetProperty
hasValue	EquipmentClassPropertyType	Value

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hasValue	EquipmentPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PersonPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PersonnelClassPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	Value
hasVendorID	PhysicalAssetType	VendorID
hasVersion	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Version
hasVersion	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Version
hasVersion	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Version
isDefineAsPersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassPropertyType
isDefineAsTestedPersonPropertyType	TestedPersonProperty	TestedPersonPropertyType
isDefineAsVersionType	Version	VersionType
isDefinedAsDescriptionType	Description	DescriptionType
isDefinedAsEquipmentAssetMappingType	EquipmentAssetMapping	EquipmentAssetMappingType
isDefinedAsEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassIDType	EquipmentClassID	EquipmentClassIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassType	EquipmentClass	EquipmentClassType
isDefinedAsEquipmentIDType	EquipmentID	EquipmentIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentInformationType	EquipmentInformation	EquipmentInformationType
isDefinedAsEquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentProperty	EquipmentPropertyType
isDefinedAsEquipmentType	Equipment	EquipmentType
isDefinedAsHierarchyScopeType	EquipmentLevel	HierarchyScopeType
isDefinedAsHierarchyScopeType	HierarchyScope	HierarchyScopeType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	FixedAssetID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	ID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	PhysicalLocation	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	VendorID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsLocationType	Location	LocationType
isDefinedAsNameType	Manufacturer	NameType

SATISFACTORY

isDefinedAsNameType	Name	NameType
isDefinedAsPersonIDType	PersonID	PersonIDType
isDefinedAsPersonNameType	PersonName	PersonNameType
isDefinedAsPersonPropertyType	PersonProperty	PersonPropertyType
isDefinedAsPersonType	Person	PersonType
isDefinedAsPersonnelClassIDType	PersonnelClassID	PersonnelClassIDType
isDefinedAsPersonnelClassType	PersonnelClass	PersonnelClassType
isDefinedAsPersonnelInformationType	PersonnelInformation	PersonnelInformationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassIDType	PhysicalAssetClassID	PhysicalAssetClassIDType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetClass	PhysicalAssetClassType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetIDType	PhysicalAssetID	PhysicalAssetIDType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetInformation	PhysicalAssetInformationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetPropertyType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetType
isDefinedAsPropertyIDType	PropertyID	PropertyIDType
isDefinedAsPublishedDateType	PublishedDate	PublishedDateType
isDefinedAsQualificationTestSpecificationIDType	QualificationTestSpecificationID	QualificationTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsQualificationTestSpecificationType	QualificationTestSpecification	QualificationTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsTestResultType	TestResult	TestResultType
isDefinedAsTestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	TestedEquipmentClassProperty	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedEquipmentPropertyType	TestedEquipmentProperty	TestedEquipmentPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	TestedPersonnelClassProperty	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	TestedPhysicalAssetProperty	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType
isDefinedAsValueType	Value	ValueType

A2.2 R3D ONTOLOGY – MODELLING DETAILS

Data Property	Domain	Range
a_type	action	string
amount	objectid	unsignedByte
amount	warehouse_element	unsignedByte
authors	procedure	string
code	action	string
code	operation	string
code	procedure	string
code	relation	string
code	step	string
code	warehouse_element	string
confidentiality_level	procedure	ConfidentialityLevel
creation_date	procedure	dateTime
description	action	string
description	operation	string
description	procedure	string
description	relation	string
description	step	string
description	warehouse_element	string
dl_type	description_layer	DescriptiveLayerType
dl_value	description_layer	string
el_type	warehouse_element	ElementType
element_id	warehouse_element	string
entry_id	objectid	string
goal	procedure	string
internal_id	action	unsignedByte
internal_id	operation	unsignedByte
internal_id	procedure	unsignedByte
internal_id	relation	unsignedByte
internal_id	step	unsignedByte
is_direct	relation	boolean
name	action	string
name	operation	string
name	procedure	string
name	relation	string
name	step	string

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name	warehouse_element	string
order	action	unsignedByte
order	operation	unsignedByte
order	procedure	unsignedByte
order	relation	unsignedByte
order	step	unsignedByte
preconditions	action	string
preconditions	operation	string
preconditions	procedure	string
preconditions	step	string
rel_type	relation	GraphElementSpecification
resource_type	description_layer	ResourceType
result	objectid	string
short_description	action	string
short_description	operation	string
short_description	procedure	string
short_description	relation	string
short_description	step	string
short_description	warehouse_element	string
source_id	relation	unsignedByte
target_id	relation	unsignedByte
version	procedure	string
weight	relation	unsignedByte